

C O N T E N T S

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	PageNo.	PDF
01	Pyeam Abbasi & Homa Pourkaramali	The Rime of the Ancient Mariner: An Ecocritical Approach	1-15	PDF
02	Abhinandan Malas	Gender Narratives and Cultural Perspectives in Girish Karnad's Yayati, Hayavadana and Naga-Mandala	16-22	PDF
03	Alpana Bhargava	Samuel Johnson: The Lexicographer	23-32	PDF
04	Dr. R. Ananthbabu	Women Empowerment: A Critical Study of Bharati Mukherjee's Wife	33-39	PDF
05	Dr. Anil S. Kapoor	Thomas Hardy: 'The Inestimably Subtle Man of Letters'	40-54	PDF
06	Anita S	Representation of Women in the Works of P.G.Wodehouse	55-58	PDF
07	Chingangbam Anupama	An Eco-Critical Approach: A Study of Selected North East Indian Poets	59-67	PDF
08	Archana M. Kulkarni	Socialism in Mulk Raj Anand's Untouchable	68-70	PDF
09	Arya P. A.	Body and Beyond: A Feminist Reading of Kamala Das' Love Poems	71-79	PDF
10	Ayusman Chakraborty	Pandurang Hari and the Criticism of British Rule in India: An Assessment	80-86	PDF
11	Badakynti Nylla langngap	A Postcolonial Reading of Isabel Allende's Eva Luna	87-95	PDF

12	Bilquees Dar	Aga Shahid Ali as a Daisporic Poet	96-99	PDF
13	Mereleen Lily Lyngdoh Y. Blah	If I Write You Are Not Dead	100-103	PDF
14	Charanpreet Randhawa	Presentation of Political Upheavals in Rohinton Mistry's Such A Long Journey	104-109	PDF
15	Mukhtar Ahmad Dar	Art and Activism: A Study of Mahasweta Devi's Mother of 1084	110-117	PDF
16	Saptorshi Das & Dr. (Prof) Arindam Modak	Sophocles' Antigone: A Feminist Representation	118-122	PDF
17	Dharmendra Singh	Torn between Two Cultures: Jhumpa Lahiri's The Namesake	123-128	PDF
18	Divya Bakshi	Detexting Hypertext	129-133	PDF
19	Farha Naz Farrukh	Feminist Perspective in Anita Desai's Where Shall We Go This Summer?	134-137	PDF
20	Farooq Ahmad Sheikh	It is all about Big God versus Small God: A Reader's Response to Chapter One of The God of Small Things	138-144	PDF
21	Firdous Ahmad Mir	Islam : V. S. Naipaul's Politics	145-155	PDF
22	Darbarsing D. Girase	Divakaruni's Arranged Marriage: A Saga of Peripheral Existence	156-160	PDF
23	Hanan Alazaz	The Word as a Sword: Linguistic Resistance in Gulliver's Travels	161-168	PDF
24	Hari Babu Thammineni	Gandhism Is Always a Powerful Tool of Social Change: A Study of Vizai Bhaskar's The Return of Gandhi	169-171	PDF
25	Dr. Harish G. Tapadia	Portrayal of Tender Brother-Sister Relationship in George Eliot's The Mill on the Floss	172-176	PDF
26	Insha Siraj	Celebrating Womanhood in Kamala Markandaya's Nectar in a Sieve	177-181	PDF
27	Aneyes Ul Islam	Reading Khaled Hosseini's A Thousand Splendid Suns as a Novel of Women Resilience	182-187	PDF
28	Jasmine Fernandez	Back to Nature: A Reading of Kiran Desai's Hullabaloo in the Guava Orchard	188-195	PDF
29	Jayanta Rana	Exploration of English as the 'Power' Language in Mulk Raj Anand's Early Novels	196-203	PDF
30	Jharana Rani Dh. Majhi	Translating the Untranslatable: The Politics of Language in the English Translation of Yajnaseni	204-209	PDF
31	Dr. Kafeel Ahmed Choudhury	The Other Feminine: Status of Women in Islam in a Globalized World	210-215	PDF

32	Kiranpreet Kaur	Do You Know Me? The Study of Fear of Losing Identity in Manto's Toba Tek Singh	216-220	PDF
33	Sk. Khamarjahan	Disquisition of Women Characters in Amitav Ghosh's The Glass Palace	221-228	PDF
34	Khushee Saroha	A Regional Study of Dalit Autobiographies from Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh and Punjab	229-238	PDF
35	Latha K. Reddy	Myth Ritual of Akkammadeities by Urumulavaru	239-243	PDF
36	Dr.Bolla.Mallikharjuna Rao	R.K.Narayan's Talkative Man: A Study in Architectonic Quality	244-248	PDF
37	Manju	Class Classification in Arnold Wesker's Roots	249-252	PDF
38	Mehvish Syed	Patriarchal Pathology: The Case of Sam Shepard's Buried Child and Mahesh Dattani's Where There's a Will	253-259	PDF
39	Misha Jose	Marriage to Morbidity: Women in Anita Desai's Cry, the Peacock and Bharathi Mukherjee's Wife	260-264	PDF
40	Mohd Mohsin	An Ecofeministic Reading of Leslie Marmon Silko's Storyteller, Lullaby and Yellow Woman	265-272	PDF
41	Dr. Mona Goel	An Analysis of Mother-Daughter Relationship in Difficult Daughters	273-278	PDF
42	Naveen Kumar Pathak	English Education: A New Mantra of Social and Economic Development in Rural India	279-281	PDF
43	Dr. Nazia Hasan	The World Breathes in Polyphony: Rushdie's Resistance to Designed Uniformity through Haroun and the Sea of Stories	282-289	PDF
44	Neelam Sanwal Bhardwaj	Enlarging the Limits of the Canvas: Feminist Perspective in Githa Hariharan's The Ghosts of Vasu Master	290-295	PDF
45	Nivedita Lahkar	The Idea of Nation as Heterogeneous: Midnight's Children and The Shadow Lines	296-298	PDF
46	Omila Thounaojam	Dislocation and Relocation in Toni Morrison's Jazz	299-305	PDF
47	Amitava Pal	Latent Lust in The Last Ride Together: A Study in Deconstruction and Psychoanalysis	306-311	PDF
48	Dr. Pallavi Banerjee	The Bluest Eye to Love: Thematic and Structural Evolution in the Fiction of Toni Morrison	312-320	PDF

49	Ram Naresh Patel	A Dalit's Voice of Oppression, Resistance and Empowerment: A Critique of K.A. Gunasekaran's The Scar	321-326	PDF
50	Dr. Susant Kumar Patnaik	Figure of Speech in R.K.Narayan's The Bachelor of Arts: A Stylistic Approach	327-334	PDF
51	Prabalika Sarma	The Portrayal of Violence in the Writings of Temsula Ao and Easterine Iralu	335-342	PDF
52	Prakash Chandra Patel	Kiran Desai's The Inheritance of Loss: A Saga of Human Relations	343-348	PDF
53	Prasanta Ghoshal	Multiplicity and 'Power' of Rituals in Shri Jagannatha Temple	349-357	PDF
54	Dr. Pratibha Kalani	The Nirvitarka Concentration as Represented in Narayan's Mr. Sampath	358-363	PDF
55	Priyanka Maral	Ecocritism in Amitav Ghosh's Sea of Poppies	364-369	PDF
56	Dr. Rajani Sharma	T. S. Eliot's The Waste Land: A Perspective on Indian Thoughts	370-377	PDF
57	Rajashree Pandiyan & Dr. Palany Arangasamy	Semiotics: A Literary Genre Universal	378-383	PDF
58	Rakhi N P	Ecological Imperialism and its New Face: The Impact of Technology, Capitalism and Colonialism on Postcolonial Ecologies	384-388	PDF
59	Ram Naresh Sah	Dalit Voices: A Comparative Study of the Novels of Mulk Raj Anand and Richard Wright	389-395	PDF
60	Prabhat Rana	Maternity "Bastilled": Vindicating the Suffering Revolutionary Women in Mary Wollstonecraft's Maria	396-401	PDF
61	S.Rangarajan	Quilting Relationships between Christopher Marlowe's Doctor Faustus and William Shakespeare's The Tempest	402-406	PDF
62	Rathod Rameshwar Balchand	A Postcolonial Interpretation of the Colonized: A Study of the Autobiographical Elements in V.S. Naipaul's The Mystic Masseur	407-410	PDF
63	Ravi Kant	Dalit Iconography and Modes of Resistance: Defying 'an Aesthetic'	411-418	PDF
64	Reshu Gupta & Vivek Gaur	Indo-English Women Poetry: A Journey from Feminism to Post-Feminism	419-423	PDF
65	Rinkoo Wadhera	Bucolic Imaginings and Urban Reality: Nissim Ezekiel's Poetry Suspended in Mid-Space	424-437	PDF
66	Rohini V. Pathak	Influence of Society in Meena Kandasamy's Social and Poetic Identity Reflected in her Poetry	438-443	PDF

67	RupaVemuri & Prof. C.L.L.Jayaprada	The Indian Urge to Rewrite: A Critical Study of Postmodern Indian English Historical Fiction	444-453	PDF
68	Dr. Sadhana Sharma	Mahasweta Devi's Outcast: Four Stories: The Subaltern do Speak	454-459	PDF
69	Sambuddha Ghosh	'The World is Like a Mask Dancing': Exploring Pluralist Paradigms of History in Chinua Achebe's Arrow of God	460-466	PDF
70	Muhammad Reza Samimi & Pyeaam Abbasi	Cultural Presuppositions in Translation from Persian into English: A Case Study of Two Persian Novels: The Blind Owl and The School Principal	467-480	PDF
71	Dr. Sandhya Gupta	Gauri Deshpande's between Births: Unravelling Poetic Sensibility	481-487	PDF
72	Sarap N.S., Mahadik R.P. & Mehta P.G.	Difficulties Faced by B.Sc. Agriculture Students in Learning and Use of English	488-497	PDF
73	P. Saravanakumar & Dr.D.Shanmugam	Seeking Comfort in the Same Sex: An Analysis of Female Characters in Anita Nair's Ladies Coupe'	498-507	PDF
74	Seema Sharma & Dr. Vidushi Sharma	Ted Hughes' Poetry of Manichaeic Paradoxes	508-513	PDF
75	Sejal Mahendru	The Interplay of Cinema and Theatre in the Shakespearean Trilogy of Lawrence Olivier	514-521	PDF
76	Shailaja A. Changundi	Dweller Diaspora in Iain M. Banks' The Algebraist	522-527	PDF
77	Farah Siddiqui	Memory as the Axis of Poetry: A Study of A.K. Ramanujan's Obituary	528-533	PDF
78	Simwa Solomon	Modernizing Genre: Subversion of the Epic in Witi Ihimaera's The Whale Rider	534-537	PDF
79	M. Sivapriya	A Seamless Transition from the Fictional to the Real in Anuradha Marwah's A Pipe Dream in Delhi	538-546	PDF
80	Smita Sahu	The Emergence of Environmental Justice in Literature	547-551	PDF
81	Dr. Sneha Gupta	Confronting Reality: A Study on Naipaul's India: A Wounded Civilization	552-558	PDF
82	Dr. Sohail Ahmed	Socio-Political Irregularities/Anarchy and Caste Aberrations in Rohinton Mistry's Such a Long Journey and A Fine Balance	559-564	PDF
83	M. Subha & Dr. T. Jayasudha	Postmodern Bricolage: A Study of Rahul Bhattacharya's The Sly Company of People who Care	565-570	PDF
84	Suchitra Pramanik	Igbo Culture as Colonial Resistance in Arrow of God	571-580	PDF

85	Sukriti Sobti	Creating Communities, Forming Families: Black Women in the American City	581-587	PDF
86	Swati Chandra	Rashsundari Debi's Amar Jiban and Binodini Dasi's My Story and My Life as an Actress: A Comparative Study	588-591	PDF
87	Tamali Bhattacharjee	Exploring the Self: A Study of Hazlitt's My First Acquaintance with Poets	592-596	PDF
88	Tripti Tyagi	Representation of History in Girish Karnad's Tughlaq	597-606	PDF
89	Dr. Vidushi Sharma	Search for Identity in the Poetry of Modern Indo-English Women Poets	607-612	PDF
90	Vivek Gaur	Interrogating the Margins through Wordsworth's Romanticism and Patanjali's Yogasutra	613-618	PDF
91	Zhou Yun	The Difficulties in Translation Work and the Role of Translator	619-622	PDF
92	Indulekha.C	The "Invisible Environmentalist" in Kamala Markandaya: An Eco Aesthetic Blend in Nectar in a Sieve	719-723	PDF
93	Jyoti Dahiya	Mrs. Dalloway: Themes and Stream of Consciousness	724-728	PDF
94	Kusum Nandal	Subaltern Children in The Bluest Eye	729-732	PDF
95	G. Vasistha Bhargavi	The Use of Nonverbal Theatrical Techniques in Soyinka's Plays	733-736	PDF
96	Vinod Kumar	India as a Contentious Image: A Study of Arundhati Roy's Listening to Grasshoppers: Field Notes on Democracy (2009)	737-744	PDF
Poetry				
01	Bhaskaranand Jha Bhaskar	Hues of Life	623	PDF
02	Jawaid Danish	Uprising ! (Translated by : Bina Biswas)	624	PDF
03	Cleber Pacheco	Visions	625	PDF
04	G David Schwartz	Socrates Had Two Knees	626	PDF
05	Frank Zahn	A Sensuous Pause	627	PDF
06	George K. Karos	The Foundry of Trapped Observations	628	PDF
07	Jonathan Doughty	Inheritance/Iteration	629	PDF
08	Lara Biyuts	Elegiac Stroll	630	PDF
09	Lovely Dutta Prusty	Maa	631-632	PDF
10	Dr. Madhuri Sood	The Old Age	633	PDF
11	Mrinal Kanti Ghosh	Rosalind I Am	634-635	PDF
12	Prabal J. Roddannavar	A Call at the Door	636-637	PDF
13	Rupesh Singh	She Walks In Beauty	638	PDF

14	Sarita Jenamani	Ascendant	639	PDF
15	Dr. Abdullah Shaghi	Un-Heavily Rained	640	PDF
16	Dr. Shalini Yadav	I am Chaste	641-642	PDF
17	Shobhana Kumar	Book of Monuments	643	PDF
18	Siam Hussain	Being a Ghost	644	PDF
19	Dr. V. Sunitha	Question Mark	645-646	PDF
20	Jawaid Danish	I Was Not Your Virgin Touch! (Translated by: Varsha Singh)	647	PDF
Fiction				
01	Bruce Colbert	Angel of the Morning	648-661	PDF
02	Iram Fatima	The Compromise	662-667	PDF
03	Jason Ford	A Signal from another Species	668-680	PDF
04	Ramesh Tiwari	Our Inspirations are the Will of God	681-686	PDF
05	Ravi Kant	The Last Draught of Water: In Retrospect	687-689	PDF
06	Rumpa Das	Puja Thoughts	690-691	PDF
Review				
01	Abu Sufian	Long Day's Journey into Night by Eugene O'Neill	692-695	PDF
02	Chittaranjan Bhoi	A Daughter Speaks (A Collection of Poems) by Shruti Das	696-700	PDF
03	Dr. Hassen ZRIBA	After the Arab Spring: How Islamists Hijacked The Middle East Revolts By John R. Bradley	701-705	PDF
04	Hiren Zala	All & Everything in Diagrams by Mohan Vaishnav	706-708	PDF
05	Ram Avadh Prajapati	The Mouth of Truth by S.C. Dwivedi	709-711	PDF
06	Varsha Singh	The Ballad of the Bleeding Bubbles; A Fabulous Bouquet of Love Poems by Ratan Bhattacharjee	712-713	PDF
07	Syeda Shahzia Batool Naqvi	Diaries of Traveler and Madman's Song by K'nitin Sarma	714-718	PDF